

Molecular Orbital Calculations on Polypeptides and Proteins

III. Conformation of Side Chains

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The conformations of side chains in polypeptides have been discussed on the basis of predictions from extended Huckel theory. For certain backbone conformations, carbon atoms at α , β , and γ positions in the side chain can have a fairly strong interaction with the atoms in the backbone and consequently such conformations become unstable with branching of side chains, or when bulky groups are present in β -positions. Beyond δ -carbon atom, the side chain conformation is independent of the backbone structure. The nature of side chain affects the relative energies for right handed α -helix and collagen structures. The right handed α -helix appear to be most stable when the side chain contains a secondary β -carbon. For all the side chains studied, the energy difference between the two structures is very small. However, such structures are fairly stable compared to left handed α -helix or extended chains.

Three approaches have been used in the study of backbone conformation of a polypeptide chain¹⁻⁴. These are based on hard sphere model (contact criterion or model building)^{1,2}, use of classical potential functions^{1,2} for nonbonded interaction and the application of molecular orbital theories^{3,4,5}. Calculations are generally made on dipeptides since these serve as good models for the polypeptides.

In the previous papers in this series³ the advantages of extended Huckel theory (EHT) over the classical methods for predicting the stable conformations of polypeptides, have been discussed in some detail. The values of ϕ , ψ and ω (denoting rotations about the N-C α , C α -C' and C'-N bonds respectively, in the polypeptide chain-NH-C α HR-C'O-) corresponding to the minimum calculated energy have been obtained. With the help of such calculations it has been shown that in general the *trans* peptides ($\omega = 0^\circ$) are more stable than *cis* peptides ($\omega = 180^\circ$). In the (ϕ , ψ) hyperspace, the energy contours for *trans*-diglycine (R = H) are fairly flat and consequently the glycylic residues have tendency to promote random coils. On the other hand, in the presence of a β -carbon atom (as in glycylic L-alanine, R = -CH₃) the regions of stability are highly restricted. Calculations on certain selected conformations show that the stability is in the sequence (100, 330) > (122, 134) > (0, 0) > (238, 226). The above four conformational angles correspond to those in collagen, right handed α -helix, fully extended chains and left hand α -helix.

1. G. N. Ramachandran and V. Sasisekharan, in "Advances in Protein Chemistry", ed. C. B. Anfinsen, M. L. Anson, J. T. Edsall and F. M. Richards, Academic Press, New York, 1968, **23**, 283.
2. H. A. Scheraga in "Advances in Physical Organic Chemistry", ed. V. Gold, Academic Press New York, 1968, **6**, 103.
3. G. Govil (a) *J. Chem. Soc.* Part I of this series : 1970, 2464.
(b) *J. Chem. Soc.* Part II of this series : 1971, 386.
4. R. Hoffmann and A. Imamura, *Biopolymers*, 1969, **7**, 207.
5. B. Maigret, B. Pullman and M. Dreyfus, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 1970, **26**, 321.

In this paper, we report the stable conformations of the side chain R, by calculating the energy as function of rotation χ_1 about the $C^\alpha-C^\beta$ bond. The effect of longer side chains and their branching on the relative stabilities of the above mentioned backbone conformations are also discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(a) *Method of Calculations* : The EHT calculations have been made on a fragment of the type $:\ddot{C}-C'O-NH-C^*RH-C'O-NH-\ddot{C}:$, composed of L-aminoacid residues in *trans*-conformation ($\omega = 0$). The valence shell ionisation potentials and the orbital exponents are the same as used in Part I of this series^{3a}. As has been pointed out in the above mentioned paper, the magnitude of the energy differences between various conformations depend somewhat on the parameters chosen but the relative stabilities of the conformations are fairly insensitive to such a choice. This provides faith in the conclusions drawn regarding molecular shapes using EHT. It may be pointed out that despite its simplicity, the predictions of conformational structure by EHT match remarkably well with those obtained by *ab initio* MO-SCF methods⁶.

The input to our programme for EHT calculations consists of precise atomic coordinates of the various atoms. These are calculated by another programme from the bond lengths, bond angles and torsional angles. The standard bond lengths and bond angles for the atoms in the backbone are given in reference (3a). The coordinates of the atoms in the side chain have been calculated using C-C and C-H bond distances of 1.53 and 1.09 Å respectively, and tetrahedral bond angles. Since we have already fixed $\omega = 0^\circ$, all the torsional angles can be calculated in terms of ϕ , ψ and χ_1 , χ_2 , χ_3 etc. The χ angles define rotations about the C-C bonds in the side chains and can be defined in a manner analogous to that in ref. (1). For example, χ_1 define rotation about $C^\alpha-C^\beta$ bond and is measured as indicated in figs. (1) to (4). Similarly, χ_2 define rotation about $C^\beta-C^\gamma$ bond, χ_3 about $C^\gamma-C^\delta$ bond and so on.

Calculations have been performed on four selected backbone conformations namely those corresponding to fully extended chain ($\phi = 0^\circ$, $\psi = 0^\circ$), collagen (100° , 330°), right handed α -helix (122° , 134°) and left handed α -helix (238° , 226°). Energies have been calculated at regular intervals of χ_1 , and the potential energy curves are shown in fig. 1 to 4. The energies corresponding to minima in these curves are given in the Table. For side chains containing γ and δ carbon atoms values of χ_2 and χ_3 for most stable conformation have also been obtained (see Table).

The following side chains have been considered :

- (i) $-\text{CH}_3$ corresponding to alanine residues.
- (ii) $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$, with a primary β -carbon atom, which can be considered as representative of leucine, methionine etc.
- (iii) $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$, which allows the determination of χ_2 and χ_3 angles in long side chains as in lysine, arginine, etc.

6. L. C. Allen and J. D. Russell, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **46**, 1029.

(iv) $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ representing valine, isoleucine, etc.

(v) $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ with a tertiary β -carbon atom. Such residues are rarely found in natural proteins.

Several amino acid residues like cysteine, serine, threonine, tyrosine, etc., have a hetero atom (O or S) or an aromatic ring at β -position and in these cases the conformational picture may be different from that of CH_2CH_3 group. For several reasons, such side chains need individual treatments and would not be discussed in this paper.

Fig. 1. The potential energy curves for dipeptide containing $-\text{CH}_3$ group in the side chain. The angle χ_1 denote rotation about $C^\alpha-C^\beta$ bond and is measured as indicated above. The backbone conformational angles are : Δ ($100^\circ, 330^\circ$); \odot ($122^\circ, 134^\circ$) \times ($0^\circ, 0^\circ$); \square ($238^\circ, 226^\circ$).

Fig. 2. Potential energy curves for $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$. With respect to rotation about $C^\beta-C^\gamma$ bond it is found that minimum energy for all the four backbone structures occur when the hydrogen atoms on C^γ acquire a staggered configuration relative to the substituents on C^α ($\chi_2 = 60, 180$ or 300°). The curves correspond to these values of χ_2 .

Fig. 3. Potential energy curves for $R = -\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ with $\chi_2 = 60^\circ$.

Fig. 4. Potential energy curves for $R = -\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$, with $\chi_2 = 60^\circ$.

(b) *Nature of Potential Energy Curves* : The conformational features of the side chain have been discussed on a classical picture by Ramachandran *et al.*¹⁷. They argue that for minimum nonbonded repulsive energies, χ_1 should be nearly equal to 60 , 180 or 300° leading to a staggered conformation. Further, the position $\chi_1 = 300^\circ$ is most favourable for occupation by a bulky group (C^rH_3 , for example), this being situated between N and H, which are of relatively small size. For similar reasons, it is argued that $\chi_1 = 60^\circ$ is most unfavourable for being occupied by bulky substituents. However, even for simple amino acids, where experimental data on side chain conformations is available, these considerations fail. For example it is $\chi_1 = 60^\circ$ position which is generally occupied by the bulky sulphur atom of cysteine and cystine.

7. A. V. Lakshminarayanan, V. Sasisekharan and G. N. Ramachandran in "Conformation of Biopolymers", ed. G. N. Ramachandran, Academic Press, New York, 1967, 1, 61.

The potential energy curves in fig. 1 to 4 amply demonstrate the limitations of such a simple approach. Although, one sees in general three minima in the potential energy curves, the position at which the minima occur are significantly shifted from the values 60 180 and 300° for a staggered conformation. What is more important is the fact that these positions depend strongly on the backbone conformations indicating thereby that a change in protein conformation (due to say, solvent or temperature) must be accompanied by rearrangements in the side chain

The potential energy curves for $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ side chains show a three fold barrier due to the molecular symmetry. While the minimum energy conformation for right handed α -helix and collagen correspond closely to staggered conformation, the χ_1 values for extended chains and left handed α -helix deviate significantly. This indicates a very strong interaction between the side chains and the backbone in these cases. As a consequence, the conformation of the side chain seems to be governed by interaction of its atoms with those in the backbone. It is clear on this picture, why the stability of the extended chains and left handed α -helix decrease with the branching of side chains and with the presence of bulky substituents. It may be pointed out in this connection that for diglycine where the side chain consists of a single hydrogen atom, the extended chains lead to a very stable structure^{3a}, and the energy of right and left handed α -helix is equal.

The potential energy curves for right handed α -helix and collagen are fairly close to one another. Except in the case of a tertiary β -carbon, the difference in stability for the two backbone structures is less than 2 Kcal. mole⁻¹ per peptide unit. When one realises that the former can have an additional stabilisation due to intrastrand hydrogen bonds and the latter through interstrand hydrogen bonds, it becomes clear that hydrogen bonds and solvent interactions may play a major role in stabilising one conformation over the other. The character of the side chain also has an important bearing on the relative stabilities of the two helices, the right handed α -helix being most stable when there is a secondary β -carbon atom, while the collagen structure is most stable for a tertiary γ -carbon.

With regard to longer side chains, it is observed that while there is a significant change in relative stabilities of the four selected backbone structures as one goes from $-\text{H}$ to $-\text{CH}_3$ and from $-\text{CH}_3$ to $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, the changes in going from $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ to $-\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$ are not significant. This shows that δ -carbon atom does not interact significantly with the atoms in backbones in any of the four conformations. In fact for $\text{R} = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ the energy with respect to χ_2 is a minimum when the δ atom acquires a *trans* configuration relative to α -carbon atom (leading to polythene type of structure) and this holds for all the four selected conformations. Thus, one can conclude that beyond the δ carbon atom, the side chain conformation is independent of the backbone structure and is governed mainly by the interactions between the substituents on *vicinal* carbon atoms.

The stability or instability caused by introduction of side chains of various sizes can be judged by taking differences in energies of the most stable structures. The difference in energy for $\text{R} = \text{H}$ and $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ is 2396 Kcal. mole⁻¹. The corresponding differences for $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ and C_2H_5 and C_2H_5 and C_3H_7 are also of the same order (2398 Kcal. mole⁻¹). Thus, one can associate an energy decrease of around 2398 Kcal. mole⁻¹ with the addition

of a CH_2 group. This value does not change appreciably with the chain length provided the additional group is attached linearly. However, the difference in energy for $\text{R} = -\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and $n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$ is around 10 Kcal. mole⁻¹. Similarly, difference in energies for $\text{R} = -\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and $\text{R} = -\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ is 2378 Kcal. mole⁻¹ which is 10 Kcal. mole⁻¹ higher than the difference of energy between $\text{R} = -\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and $\text{R} = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$. On this basis one concludes that the branching of side chain leads to instability. It is difficult to say at the present moment if this factor is responsible for the absence of side chains containing tertiary β -carbon atoms in natural proteins.

TABLE

Energies for the most stable side chain conformations for certain selected backbone conformations

Backbone conformation (ϕ, ψ)	Most stable side chain conformations			Energy in Kcal mole ⁻¹	
	χ_1	χ_2	χ_3	Total Energy	Relative to $\phi = 0, \psi = 0$
<i>R = -H</i>					
(100, 330)				-22761.5	1.7
(122, 134)				-22760.1	3.1
(0, 0)				-22763.2	0.0
(238, 226)				-22760.1	3.1
<i>R = -CH₃</i>					
(100, 330)	65,185,305			-25158.9	-5.4
(122, 134)	60,180,300			-25157.4	-3.9
(0, 0)	60,180,300			-25153.5	0.0
(238, 226)	70,190,310			-25150.4	3.1
<i>R = -CH₂CH₃</i>					
(100, 330)	290	60,180,300		-27556.4	-7.5
(122, 134)	190	"		-27554.8	-5.9
(0, 0)	60	"		-27548.9	0.0
(238, 226)	210	"		-27545.7	3.2
<i>R = -CH₂CH₂CH₃</i>					
(0, 0)	60	180	60,180,300	-29946.6	0.0
(100, 330)	290	"	"	-29954.3	-7.7
(122, 134)	185	"	"	-29952.3	-5.7
(238, 226)	210	"	"	-29942.9	3.7
<i>R = -CH(CH₃)₂</i>					
(100, 330)	295	60		-29941.8	-24.8
(122, 330)	180	"		-29944.1	-27.1
(0, 0)	90	"		-29917.0	0.0
(238, 226)	200	"		-29930.6	13.6
<i>R = -C(CH₃)₃</i>					
(100, 330)	60,180,300	60		-32321.7	-97.7
(122, 134)	50,170,290	"		-32310.7	-76.7
(0, 0)	15,135,255	"		-32224.0	0.0
(238, 226)	85,205,325	"		-32200.1	24.1

The following general conclusions can be drawn from the above discussion :

- (i) With respect to χ_1 the potential energy curves show three minima which are somewhat different from the values in a truly staggered conformation.
- (ii) The most stable side chain conformation depends on the values of ϕ and ψ .
- (iii) For linear side chains containing more than two carbon atoms, the backbone atoms have very little interaction with δ and distant atoms and the conformation of the side chain beyond δ -carbon does not depend on the backbone.
- (iv) Branching of side chains leads to larger instability in regions other than those corresponding to right handed α -helix and collagen.
- (v) If stabilisation due to intra and interstrand hydrogen bonds are assumed to be equal then the right handed α -helix is found to be more stable for $R = -CH(CH_3)_2$. In all other cases collagen helices are more stable.

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